

PLANNING THE MEDITERRANEAN SEA

12 · 13 December 2018 | Final conference

Joint Final Conference of SUPREME and SIMWESTMED

METHODS & TOOLS: Mixed Working Groups

Minutes – *Land-Sea Interactions* working group

The workshop gathered participants from the final conference in a round of workshops. The LSI workshop, animated by PAP/RAC and supported by the CPMR, opened an informal discussion on several aspects and experiences related to LSI in MSP.

Three main questions were originally planned, but the animation adapted to the participants and covered other aspects.

Main questions:

1. How LSI is taken into consideration in Maritime Spatial Planning?
2. What are the most important aspects to be consider in LSI in MSP?
3. Do you know any areas where the LSI methodology could be tested?

After presenting the methodological guidelines for assessing LSI (as developed as part of the SUPREME and SIMWESTMED projects) developed by the PAP/RAC, the participants were invited to reply and give their thoughts about those three questions and share any experiences they might have on LSI in their country.

The main conclusions are:

- LSI is applied or can be applied in different frameworks and concepts. Some countries already take it into account as part of their spatial planning system (Croatia), others, like Spain, don't know yet how to address it.
- LSI brings more knowledge in MSP, for example more and new data on uses to be considered in MSP. It helps to scan the expectations of all sectors concerned by a plan.
- Utilising the methodological guidelines for assessing LSI can be considered as a checklist in planning systems even in the area where LSI is already part of the planning system.
- Methodological guidelines can serve to address several issues which are not taken into consideration in other planning framework, such as coastal erosion. It can be used a tool for stakeholder engagement, for communication and to raise awareness the public on MSP.
- The most challenging aspects relate to governance component of LSI. Nevertheless, it can be used as a link between different governance levels (local, regional, national, European) in addressing some specific issues.
- Reflecting on LSI is a way to adapt the framework you consider.
- LSI could be in preference tested at local level, such as in Marseille area. Other examples such as Intermunicipal plans in the Baltic are concrete examples showing the effectiveness of considering LSI in planning at local level.